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The role of complementary interregional linkages for functional upgrading and downgrading of global value chains in EU regions

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies the role of complementary interregional value chain linkages in functional upgrading and downgrading in global value chains in EU regions. It adopts an evolutionary approach to assess functional upgrading and downgrading using relatedness and economic complexity metrics. The empirical analysis of 199 EU regions between the years 2000 and 2010 shows that, while local capabilities remain crucial, complementary interregional value chain linkages increase (decrease) the likelihood of functional upgrading (downgrading) in GVCs. Regions engaged in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are more likely to specialise in more complex functions and to retain such specialisations over time. By doing so, this paper proposes a new theoretical-analytical framework to identify partner regions that can offer complementary capabilities in GVCs.

KEYWORDS

Global value chains; upgrading/downgrading; interregional linkages; complementary capabilities; EU regions

JEL CLASSIFICATION

F14; F63; O19; R11; R12

1. Introduction

The spatial fragmentation of production processes has fostered the rise of global value chains (GVCs) and functional specialisation in trade of countries and regions (Antràs 2020; Gereffi 1999; Los, Timmer, and De Vries 2015; Timmer et al. 2015, 2019). Regions differ in the production functions they develop in GVCs: while some regions concentrate on headquarters and R&D facilities, other regions have become locations of factories and logistic hubs (Blažek 2016; Crescenzi, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2014; Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon 2005). Since different production functions are associated with different levels of value added, a crucial challenge for regions is to functionally upgrade in GVCs and to avoid downgrading (Giuliani, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2005; Humphrey and Schmitz 2002; Iammarino and McCann 2013; Morrison, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2008; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti 2007, 2011; Timmer and Pahl 2021).

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To climb the ladder of functions in GVCs, regions can leverage on their own local capabilities. There is strong evidence in Evolutionary Economic Geography (EEG) that highlights the importance of local capabilities for regional diversification (Balland et al. 2019; Boschma, Balland, and Kogler 2015; Boschma 2017; Frenken, Van Oort, and Verburg 2007; Hidalgo et al. 2007, 2018; Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011; Petralia, Balland, and Morrison 2017; Rigby 2015). However, regions can also exploit non-local sources of knowledge through the inflow of MNEs (Cantwell and Iammarino 2000, 2005; Crescenzi, Dyèvre, and Neffke 2022; Crescenzi, Gagliardi, and Iammarino 2015; Elekes, Boschma, and Lengyel 2019; Neffke et al. 2018), FDI (Crescenzi and Iammarino 2017; Gagliardi, Iammarino, and Rodríguez-Pose 2021; Iammarino 2018) and high-skilled migrants (Breschi and Lissoni 2009; Breschi et al. 2020; Breschi, Lissoni, and Miguelez 2017; Diodato, Morrison, and Petralia 2022; Miguelez and Moreno 2018; Morrison 2023), among other mechanisms.

These non-local capabilities are particularly relevant in GVCs (Crescenzi and Harman 2023). Regions are not isolated islands of production, but they are rather connected through input-output linkages from which regions can learn (De Marchi, Giuliani, and Rabellotti 2018; Gereffi 1994, 1999; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti 2007, 2011; Storper 1993). Flows of intermediate products, services, and value added within and across value chains can act as knowledge pipelines, bringing new capabilities to regions (Bathelt, Malmberg, and Maskell 2004; Fusillo et al. 2024; Fusillo, Montresor, and Marzetti 2024; Maskell, Bathelt, and Malmberg 2006; Morrison, Rabellotti, and Zirulia 2013; Saliola and Zanfei 2009). Regions can benefit from participating in GVCs by learning from partner regions providing new capabilities (Frenken, Neffke, and van Dam 2023).

This paper highlights that GVCs act as a key source of non-local capabilities that may contribute to functional upgrading but may also prevent processes of functional downgrading in regions. However, we argue that value chain linkages *per se* might not matter, but rather value chain linkages with regions that offer complementary capabilities (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma and Iammarino 2009). That is, we suggest that linkages with regions with the same or unrelated functions in GVCs do not provide relevant capabilities from which regions can learn. Instead, we argue that linkages with regions that provide access to functions in GVCs that are related but missing in the region can effectively trigger the building of new capabilities and foster functional upgrading and prevent functional downgrading to take place (Boschma 2024; Sebestyén, Braun, and Elekes 2024).

This paper presents an empirical analysis of the role of complementary inter-regional linkages on functional upgrading and downgrading in GVCs in 199 EU regions between the years 2000 and 2010. We build upon the relatedness/complexity approach to functional upgrading and downgrading in GVCs proposed by Hernández-Rodríguez et al. (2025) and extend it to incorporate the role of non-local complementary capabilities. Results show indeed that complementary inter-regional value chain linkages are associated with a higher likelihood of functional upgrading in GVCs. Regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are more likely to specialise in more complex functions. On the other hand, complementary interregional value chain linkages are associated with a lower likelihood of functional downgrading in GVCs. Regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are less likely to

lose their specialisation in complex functions. Furthermore, results highlight that local capabilities are also crucial for both promoting functional upgrading and avoiding functional downgrading. The effect of local capabilities turns out to be stronger than the one of inter-regional complementary linkages. What is more, the importance of non-local complementary capabilities decreases when regions already have strong local capabilities, pointing towards a substitution effect between the two.

These findings respond to a need echoed lately by scholars to integrate more tightly the EEG and GVCs literatures (Boschma 2022, 2024; Lee 2024; Rodríguez-Pose 2021; H. W. C. Yeung 2021, 2024). This paper highlights how local and non-local complementary capabilities are crucial to better understand the evolution of GVCs, such as functional upgrading and downgrading (De Propris 2024; Poon 2024). Furthermore, it underlines the role of interregional linkages in regional diversification and new path development dynamics, which has been understudied until recently (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma 2017; Trippl, Grillitsch, and Isaksen 2018). Finally, this paper provides a framework for identifying EU partner regions providing complementary capabilities in GVCs. Such a framework can identify untapped learning opportunities for regions involved in GVCs (Giustolisi, Benner, and Trippl 2023; Radosevic and Stancova 2015). This can contribute to enhancing interregional collaboration in the EU, which still remains underexploited (Bachtrögler-Unger et al. 2023).

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 includes an overview of the relevant literature. Section 3 explains the dataset and the main variables used. Section 4 describes the empirical framework. Section 5 discusses the results. Section 6 concludes, outlines some potential public policy implications, and suggests venues for future research.

2. Interregional linkages and (down-) upgrading in GVCs

Around 70% of international trade worldwide involves global value chains (OECD 2023). Regions engage in GVCs by specialising in certain functions along production processes, rather than producing products and services from its conception to its delivery to final consumers (Antràs 2020; Coveri and Zanfei 2023; Gereffi 1999; Los, Timmer, and De Vries 2015; Timmer et al. 2015, 2019). Different functions produce different levels of value added: R&D and management activities are associated with higher value added than assembling or packaging (Blažek 2016; Crescenzi, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2014; Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon 2005; Riccio, Dosi, and Virgillito 2024). A key challenge for regions in GVCs is to move up towards high value added functions and to retain them over time (Blažek 2016; Giuliani, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2005; Humphrey and Schmitz 2002; Iammarino and McCann 2013; Kano, Tsang, and Yeung 2020; Morrison, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2008; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti 2007, 2011; Pipkin and Fuentes 2017; Plank and Staritz 2015; Timmer and Pahl 2021).

Recent contributions on GVCs have started to apply the regional diversification framework (Boschma 2017; Hidalgo et al. 2007, 2018; Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011) to GVC upgrading and downgrading dynamics (Boschma 2022, 2024; Hernández-Rodríguez et al. 2025; Koch 2021; Sebestyén, Braun, and Elekes 2024). These studies

highlight that local related capabilities are crucial to understand the evolution of GVCs.¹ They also have introduced revealed economic complexity metrics to identify upgrading and downgrading in GVCs (Hernández-Rodríguez et al. 2025), instead of using predefined functions in GVCs, as done in the smiling curve literature (Capello and Dellisanti 2024; Mudambi 2008; Shin, Kraemer, and Dedrick 2012; Stöllinger 2021). Using a relatedness/complexity framework on GVC (Boschma 2022, 2024), Hernández-Rodríguez et al. (2025) found that local capabilities enhance the chances of functional upgrading and lower the chances of functional downgrading in regions.

However, much less is known about the role of interregional linkages in regional diversification (Fold 2014; Boschma 2017; Tripl, Grillitsch, and Isaksen 2018; Balland and Boschma 2021; Qiao 2023; Qiao and Wu 2024). These interregional linkages can take several forms through the participation of MNEs (Cantwell and Iammarino 2000, 2005; Crescenzi, Dyèvre, and Neffke 2022; Crescenzi, Gagliardi, and Iammarino 2015; Elekes, Boschma, and Lengyel 2019; Qiao, Ascani, and Morrison 2024), FDI (Crescenzi and Iammarino 2017; Gagliardi, Iammarino, and Rodríguez-Pose 2021; Iammarino 2018) and inflow of high-skilled migrants (Breschi and Lissoni 2009; Breschi et al. 2020; Breschi, Lissoni, and Miguelez 2017; Diodato, Morrison, and Petralia 2022; Miguelez and Moreno 2018; Morrison 2023), among others. The GVC and international trade literatures have shown how input–output relationships through value added exchanges in production processes can act as global knowledge pipelines (Altenburg 2006; Dollar, Wolff, and Baumol 1988; Gereffi 1994, 1999; Gereffi et al. 2001; Grossman and Helpman 1991, 1993; Humphrey and Schmitz 2002; Kaplinsky 2000; Keller 2004; Morrison, Rabellotti, and Zirulia 2013; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti 2007, 2011). For example, Ivarsson and Alvstam (2011) showed how IKEA's suppliers use IKEA's technological support to upgrade their operational, duplicative, adaptive, and innovative capabilities. Caliri et al. (2023) explored the link between a country's position in the aerospace global value chain and the strength of its innovation system, underlying differences depending on which functions countries are specialised in. Delera et al. (2022) found that a firm's participation in GVCs is positively associated with the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies in developing countries.

In this vein, Morrison, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti (2008) proposed a framework to approach learning and innovation in global value chains based on the notion of technological capabilities. Taking an evolutionary approach, and following Lall (1992), they distinguish three different kinds of technological capabilities: investment, production, and linkage capabilities. First, investment capabilities refer to the abilities required before and during the investment, such as defining the required technologies and human capital. Second, production capabilities refer to the skills needed to develop the operations, like managerial and industrial engineering knowledge. Third, linkage capabilities include skills related to making connections with other actors to ensure technology linkages. On the one hand, production capabilities can be understood as local capabilities. On the other hand, linkage capabilities mainly refer to the ability of being connected and absorb external knowledge from interregional linkages (Antonelli 2000). Hence, regions can combine their existing production capabilities with those from other regions by building interregional linkages. Particularly, regions participating in GVCs can access

¹Kishimoto (2004) hinted already on the importance of local capabilities when studying the Taiwanese computer industry: previous knowledge in related production stages in the industry was required to get new orders.

non-local knowledge and trigger functional upgrading by learning from partner regions (Boschma 2022, 2024; Frenken, Neffke, and van Dam 2023).

However, previous studies on interregional linkages have underlined that connectivity is not *per se* a sufficient condition for triggering regional diversification (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma and Iammarino 2009; Corrocher, Grabner, and Morrison 2024). These studies have rather underlined the importance of complementary interregional linkages: being connected to external sources of knowledge is not *per se* sufficient to acquire new capabilities. Regions might only benefit from interregional linkages when these linkages are complementary to existing capabilities already present in the region (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma and Iammarino 2009).

A similar point has been made by the GVC literature. Regional participation in global value chains will not be automatically translated into a transfer and acquisition of new capabilities (Giuliani, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2005; Morrison, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2008, 2013; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti 2007, 2011). The benefits derived from GVC participation will, of course, depend on several aspects, such as the role of MNEs and their willingness to share knowledge, regions' absorptive capacity, the presence of strong regional institutions, and the role of power in the governance of value chains (Amendolagine, Crescenzi, and Rabellotti 2024; Cantwell and Iammarino 2000, 2005; Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon 2005; Gibbon and Ponte 2008; Humphrey and Schmitz 2000; Morrison, Rabellotti, and Zirulia 2013; Rodríguez-Pose 2021).

However, participation in GVCs in which partner regions can offer complementary capabilities may have an impact. In this context, Mäkitie et al. (2022) have theorised complementarity formation mechanisms within and across technology value chains. They distinguished three different complementarity formation mechanisms: synchronisation, amplification, and integration. Such trade linkages have been traditionally highlighted as relevant for promoting the diffusion of technology and knowledge in open economies (Dosi and Soete 1988; Fagerberg 1987, 1995). By engaging in GVCs, regions have access to new and related knowledge that can help them to upgrade into more complex functions. Among the different channels through which complementary interregional linkages can promote knowledge exchange, background engineering, learning by importing, and learning by exporting can be underlined (Andersson, Bjerke, and Karlsson 2013; Mazzi, Ndubuisi, and Avenyo 2024). Following this logic, we formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1a: Regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are more likely to specialise in new functions.

However, not all functions in GVCs are expected to bring the same benefits to regions (Capello and Dellisanti 2024; Mudambi 2008; Shin, Kraemer, and Dedrick 2012; Stöllinger 2021). Particularly, complex activities can promote stronger economic growth (Balland and Rigby 2017; Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009; Mewes and Broekel 2022; Pintar and Scherngell 2020; Rigby et al. 2022). While regions may be interested in moving towards new functions in GVCs regardless of its complexity to open future development and upgrading paths, complex functions are usually more attractive. Nevertheless, such complex functions in GVCs are also more difficult to be carried out. To specialise into complex activities, more capabilities are required (Pinheiro et al. 2025). Therefore,

regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities can build upon such related functions to become specialised in not just new, but also complex functions in GVCs. Then, we formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1b: Regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are more likely to specialise in complex functions.

In addition, once regions are globally integrated by developing functions in GVCs, they would want to keep such functional specialisations over time. In other words, they would like to avoid functional downgrading (Blažek 2016; Gereffi 2019). To do so, regions can benefit from learning from other trade-partner regions in GVCs offering new knowledge (Dosi and Soete 1988; Fagerberg 1987, 1995). Particularly, complementary capabilities can contribute to keep specialisation across functions since they provide valuable new and related knowledge (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma and Iammarino 2009). This can be crucial to guarantee that locally integrated industrial districts benefit from international production to ensure their competitiveness at a global scale (Breznitz, Bucuni, and Murphree 2024). We formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2a: Regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are more likely to preserve their specialisation in functions.

In a similar vein as hypothesis 1b, regions may also be more interested in keeping their specialisation in complex functions in GVCs. Since complex activities are expected to bring stronger economic growth (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009; Mewes and Broekel 2022; Pintar and Scherngell 2020; Rigby et al. 2022), regions will try to avoid losing their specialisation in such functions in GVCs. However, to keep their specialisations, regions require a strong embeddedness of related capabilities (D. F. Kogler, Esslezichler, and Rigby 2017; D. Kogler, Rigby, and Tucker 2013; Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011; Rigby 2015). In particular, being connected to partner regions in GVCs that offer complementary capabilities can facilitate the exchange of knowledge, promoting a stronger embeddedness for the complex functions and thus, allowing regions to preserve their specialisation in the future. We formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2b: Regions participating in GVCs in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities are more likely to preserve their specialisation in complex functions.

3. Data and variables

3.1. Data and functions in GVCs

This paper studies the role of complementary interregional value chain linkages in functional upgrading and downgrading in EU regions. For such purpose, we proxy functions in GVCs using occupation-industry pairs. Examples of functions are ‘office clerks in manufacturing and mining’, ‘drivers and mobile-plant operators in manufacturing and mining’, and ‘office clerks in financial intermediation’.

While there are alternative views on how functions (and/or tasks) should be identified, similar approaches have been used in many contributions (Deegan et al. 2024; Goos and Manning 2007; Henning and Eriksson 2021; Henning and Kekezi 2023).

We consider the exports of functions in GVCs as the exports of domestic value added generated by each function (occupation-industry pair). This computation roughly takes two steps, following Timmer, Miroudot, and de Vries (2019) and Hernández-Rodríguez et al. (2025). First, input-output tables are used to map the gross export of goods and services from a region to the domestic value added generated by each industry. Subsequently, this value added is distributed across functions based on occupational and wage data. It is also important to highlight that functions' exports are not only from an exporting industry itself but rather all domestic functions along the value chains. This is particularly important for functions in services since most of their exported value added is rather embedded in the exports of goods.

The recently developed interregional input-output tables (e.g. Huang and Koutroumpis 2023; Thissen et al. 2018) provide valuable sources to trace domestic value added in regional exports. This paper uses EUREGIO (Thissen et al. 2018) which contains information on input-output relationships for 249 regions from 24 European countries, 16 non-EU countries, a rest of the world section, and 14 industries for the period 2000–2010. While EUREGIO allows to compute the domestic value added content of gross exports and the bilateral value added flows across EU regions, uncovering functional specialisation requires labour data. For this purpose, we use Eurostat's microdata on occupations and wages from the European Union Labour Force Survey (EULFS) and the European Union Structure of Earnings Survey (EUSES). These two databases allow us to compute the income share of each function across EU regions. First, we use EULFS to know how workers are distributed across occupations within each regional industry. Second, we use the median wage of each occupation in each regional industry derived from EUSES and multiply it with the number of workers taken from EULFS to compute the income shares across functions. Subsequently, using the income share of each function, the domestic value added content of gross exports is distributed across functions. This allows us to trace the value added produced by each function (occupation-industry pair) in each region and time period.

However, it is important to highlight that there are some incompatibilities between the datasets (EUREGIO, EULFS and EUSES). First, the matching between regions is not always possible between the three databases, leading to the loss of a small number of regions. Second, EUREGIO and EULFS are at NUTS-2 level, while EUSES is at NUTS-1. We assumed wages are homogeneous across NUTS-2 within NUTS-1 when computing occupational income shares. Third, due to changes in the categorisation of occupation (from ISCO-88 to ISCO-08) in EUSES, only data for the years 2002 and 2006 is used, assuming linear interpolation between these years and keeping fixed the values for the years before 2002 and after 2006. Considering that the EULFS only uses ISCO-88, and that there is not a perfect match between ISCO-88 and ISCO-08, only two digits ISCO-88 is used. Fourth, the industrial classification of EUREGIO was followed since it is more aggregated than in

EULFS and EUSES. Finally, to overcome some missing values in EUSES, and to ensure that the functions have a minimum threshold of relevance in the economies of regions, we follow the same criteria as in Hernández-Rodríguez et al. (2025).²

The final database consists of a panel on domestic value added content of gross exports and interregional value added flows for 199 EU NUTS-2 regions and 77 functions (occupation-industry pairs) for the period 2000–2010.³ It is completed with a set of control variables: GDP per capita, population density, patent applications, and an indicator for total GVC participation. All control variables are retrieved from Eurostat with the exception of the total GVC participation, which was taken from EUREGIO. Finally, to smooth out the yearly fluctuations, the data is divided into average matrices for four non-overlapping time windows ($t = 2000–2001, 2002–2004, 2005–2007, 2008–2010$).

3.2. Functional specialisation, local capabilities and complementary interregional capabilities

Following Timmer, Miroudot, and de Vries (2019), a Functional Specialisation Index (FSI) for each region r , function s and time t is computed as follows:

$$FSI_{rst} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \frac{f_{rt}^s / \sum_s f_{rt}^s}{\sum_r f_{rt}^s / \sum_r \sum_s f_{rt}^s} \geq 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

²First, the region in which workers live was used when the region of the workplace was missing. Second, for some regions the data on wages was missing in the EUSES. Then, it was assumed that in Belgian regions, occupation (ISCO-88) 11 earns as 12, 61 as 71, and 92 as 93. In German regions, occupation 92 earns as 93, and 13 as 24. In Luxembourg occupation 61 earns as 71, and 92 as 93. Also, for Luxembourg and Portugal, wages for mining and energy were proxied by manufacturing. Third, when data for some countries was missing in the EUSES, similar criteria than Timmer, Miroudot, and de Vries (2019) were followed and adjusted for the regional level: data for Slovakia was used for Slovenia, data from Finland was used for Austria, data from BE10 was used for DK01, and data from BE30 was used for the remaining of Danish regions. Finally, as pointed out in detail in Hernández-Rodríguez et al. (2025), some restrictions were imposed to ensure a balance between the number of functions included in the analysis and their economic significance. Since some occupation-industry combinations were uncommon and contributed with very little value added, the following exclusions were applied. In the first place, both agricultural and education occupations were excluded. EUREGIO does not include information on the agricultural and public sector industries, thus, since these occupations are usually developed within them, they were excluded. Second, to avoid functions contributing with extremely low value added, we combined functions in which the sum of value added from an occupation across all sectors was lower than the 1% of the total domestic value added. This ensured that when applying the economic complexity methods, no small function will bias the results. Third, we required that the sum of value added from a sector for all its occupations should consist of at least 5% of the total domestic value added. This follows the same logic than we did before for occupations but applied to industries. This led to a merging between some sectors such as ‘manufacturing’ and ‘mining’, for example. Finally, a joint condition for both occupations and industries was applied: we excluded the smallest functions (cumulative 0.5% of total domestic value added). These correspond to very uncommon industry-occupation combinations like ‘life scientist’ in ‘logistics’.

³The final number of NUTS-2 regions included in the empirical analysis is 199. Appendix A includes a detailed list of these 199 regions, as well as for the 77 considered functions. Due to some data limitations and incompatibilities between the EUREGIO, EULFS, and the EUSES databases, some regions could not be included. Particularly, data for Romania and Bulgaria is not regionalised in EUREGIO. Furthermore, data for the UK and the Netherlands had similar issues in the EULFS and the EUSES, preventing its matching with EUREGIO. However, we believe that the representativeness of the sample is ensured since it includes the vast majority of European regions. In addition, losing observations mainly from the UK and the Netherlands should not be a major concern. These two countries primary include highly developed regions with extensive local related capabilities (Bishop and Gripiaios 2010; Frenken, Van Oort, and Verburg 2007). These highly developed regions are expected to be in a better position to gain complex functions in GVCs due to their stock of strong local related capabilities (Pinheiro et al. 2025). For further details regarding the matching process see Hernández-Rodríguez et al. (2025).

where f_{rt}^s represents the exports of functions in GVCs as defined in Section 3.1. The FSI is a binary variable measuring revealed comparative advantages, as in Balassa (1965) but based on functions in GVCs.

Then, regions move towards new functions in GVCs and exit from existing ones. As explained before, this evolution is unlikely to be random but rather path dependent in relation with local related capabilities and complementary interregional capabilities (Balland et al. 2019; Hidalgo et al. 2007; Neffke, Henning, and Boschma 2011; Rigby 2015). The first step is to compute the degree of relatedness between the 77 considered functions in GVCs, following Hidalgo et al. (2007):

$$\phi_{s_i, s_j, t} = \min \left\{ P \left(FSI_{s_i, t} = 1 | FSI_{s_j, t} = 1 \right), P \left(FSI_{s_j, t} = 1 | FSI_{s_i, t} = 1 \right) \right\} \quad (2)$$

The degree of relatedness (ϕ) between two functions (s_i, s_j) is computed by the minimum value of the pairwise conditional probability of a region being specialised ($FSI = 1$) in a function given that it is also specialised in another one in period t , where the conditional probabilities are derived from the observational co-occurrence of the two functions in each region.

The second step is to regionalise these data and compute a relatedness density measure after Hidalgo et al. (2007). The local relatedness density (LRD) for each region r and a particular function s_i at time t is obtained by adding all the relatedness values of the other functions that are related to s_i , and in which region r is specialised in (i.e. the dummy FSI equals to 1):

$$\text{Local Relatedness Density}_{r, s_i, t} = \frac{\sum_s FSI_{rst} \phi_{s, s_i, t}}{\sum_s \phi_{s, s_i, t}} \quad (3)$$

Second, we measure the role of complementary interregional linkages for functional upgrading and downgrading. As previously discussed, complementary interregional linkages can complement existing local capabilities to move up and climb the ladder of functions in GVCs. Following a similar logic proposed by Balland and Boschma (2021) who used co-inventor linkages to measure complementary linkages, we use value added flows instead. We propose a new measure of complementary relatedness density for functions in GVCs. We compute a bilateral complementarity relatedness density (BCRD) that a region r can obtain from a trade partner p for a particular function s_i , which can be formulated as follows:

$$BCRD_{r, p, s_i, t} = \frac{\sum_{s \neq s_i} FSI_{p, s, t} (1 - FSI_{r, s, t}) \phi_{s, s_i, t}}{\sum_s \phi_{s, s_i, t}} \quad (4)$$

BCRD is derived from functions in which the partner region p has a comparative advantage ($FSI_{pst} = 1$) in which region r is not specialised ($FSI_{rst} = 0$). This is the potential complementary effect that region r may obtain from its trade partner p . BCRD will be high if the partner region p is specialised in many functions s that are closely related with s_i , in which region r does not have a specialisation. BCRD will be zero when regions r and p have an identical pattern of functional specialisation, meaning there is no complementarity.

Since regions are differently connected to their partners in terms of input-output linkages, it is necessary to weight BCRD by the strength of such linkages. We weigh the BCRD by bilateral value added trade flows (VAT), such that the complementarity relatedness density for a function s_i that region r derives from all its trade partners is given by:

$$\text{Complementary relatedness density}_{r,s_i,t} = \sum_{p \neq r} \frac{VAT_{prt}}{\sum_{p \neq r} VAT_{prt}} BCRD_{r,p,s_i,t} \quad (5)$$

Value-added trade is more relevant than gross exports because we want to capture the knowledge a region can learn from trade-related value-adding activities conducted by its trade partner. To be specific, we measure value added trade by the domestic value added contributed by the partner region p that is embedded in its gross export to region r . Our measure is in analogy with the concept of a country's domestic value added in gross export (see Koopman, Wang, and Wei 2014; Timmer, Miroudot, and de Vries 2019), but in a bilateral setting. With EUREGIO data, we use a standard input-output approach to derive bilateral value added trade flows between regions:

$$VAT_{prt} = \mathbf{v}'_{pt} (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_{pt})^{-1} \mathbf{E}_{prt} \quad (6)$$

Assuming there are in total G industries. \mathbf{E}_{prt} is a G -element vector denoting gross export of each kind of goods and services from region p to r in year t . \mathbf{A}_{pt} is the domestic input-output table of region p with a dimension of $G \times G$, such that $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}_{pt})^{-1}$ is the Leontief-inverse which maps the gross export flows to the required domestic gross output production in each industry. \mathbf{v}_{pt} is a G -element vector for the value added to gross output ratio in each industry.

It should be noticed that, preferably, the complementarity relatedness density for a region should be computed from all its potential trade partners in the entire world. We only have functional data for 199 NUTS regions in the EU (see Appendix A). As a result, we miss out part of the complementarity relatedness density, and the indices will be underestimated if a region has strong linkages with non-EU countries and EU regions for which data is not available. We will mitigate this issue by including region and function fixed effects in the regressions. We believe that the underestimation is consistent for each region and can be alleviated by the fixed effects since the composition of regions' trade partners is largely stable over time.

3.3. Upgrading, downgrading and economic complexity

Our aim is to investigate the influence of the local relatedness density and the complementary relatedness density on the evolution of functional specialisations of regions. We will perform regression analyses (in Section 4) on the dependent variables that captures regions' entrance/exits from functions, as well as the regions' functional upgrading and downgrading.

Functional diversification refers to the entry of new functions in general. Formally, a region enters into a new comparative advantage which it did not possess in the previous time window:

$$\text{Diversification}_{rst} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 1 \text{ and } FSI_{rs,t-1} = 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 0 \text{ and } FSI_{rs,t-1} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

In a similar vein, functional exit is defined as a loss of a specialisation in a function, in which the region was specialised in the previous time window.

$$\text{Exit}_{rst} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 0 \text{ and } FSI_{rs,t-1} = 1 \\ 0 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 1 \text{ and } FSI_{rs,t-1} = 1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

We also analyse a refined subset to capture the upgrading and downgrading of GVC functions in each region. For this purpose, we employ economic complexity metrics. Economic complexity has been shown to positively correlate with economic growth of countries and regions (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009; Mewes and Broekel 2022; Pintar and Scherngell 2020; Rigby et al. 2022). Moving into more (less) complex functions can then be understood as functional upgrading (downgrading) in GVCs.

Such economic complexity indicators are computed by the method of reflections (Hidalgo and Hausmann 2009). We compute a set of FSI_{rs} based on the average f_{rt}^s between the years 2000–2010, to construct an $R \times S$ matrix (R is the number of regions and S functions), M , indicating whether a region on average has a comparative advantage in a function over the period. We compute the number of functions in which each region has a comparative advantage (diversity), and how common are functional specialisations across regions (ubiquity):

$$\text{Diversity}_r = K_{r0} = \sum_s M_{rs} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Ubiquity}_s = K_{s0} = \sum_r M_{rs} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, functions in GVCs will be considered as complex by fulfilling two criteria: when they are not common (low ubiquity), and when they are developed by regions that are also specialised in many other functions (high diversity) (Balland et al. 2022). Then, the economic complexity of both regions (FCI_r) and functions (FCI_s) can be obtained using the following iteration of n rounds.

$$FCI_r = K_{rn} = \frac{1}{K_{r0}} \sum_s M_{rs} K_{s,n-1} \quad (11)$$

$$FCI_s = K_{sn} = \frac{1}{K_{s0}} \sum_r M_{rs} K_{r,n-1} \quad (12)$$

We exploit the differences in the economic complexity of functions (FCI_s) to empirically define upgrading and downgrading in GVCs. Functional upgrading means a region enters into a new function s with a higher complexity than the previous national average. To be more precise, $FCI_s > \overline{FCI}_{r,t-1}$, where $\overline{FCI}_{r,t-1} = \sum_s (FCI_s \times FSI_{rs,t-1}) / \sum_s FSI_{rs,t-1}$ is the average of the FCI_s in which the region was specialised in the previous period. Therefore, in the regression analyses, we are interested in the probability for a region to upgrade to the new functions s in the set of $FSI_{rs,t-1} = 0$ and $FCI_s > \overline{FCI}_{r,t-1}$, formally defined as:

$$\text{Upgrading}_{rst} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 1, FSI_{rs,t-1} = 0, \text{ and } FCI_s > \overline{FCI}_{r,t-1} \\ 0 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 0, FSI_{rs,t-1} = 0, \text{ and } FCI_s > \overline{FCI}_{r,t-1} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Similarly, we will also test the probability of downgrading, i.e. the loss of a specialisation in a function with a higher-than-average complexity:

$$\text{Downgrading}_{rst} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 0, FSI_{rs,t-1} = 1, \text{ and } FCI_s > \overline{FCI}_{r,t-1} \\ 0 & \text{if } FSI_{rst} = 1, FSI_{rs,t-1} = 1, \text{ and } FCI_s > \overline{FCI}_{r,t-1} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

3.4. An illustrative example of complementarity relatedness density in the Italian region of Friuli-Venezia Giulia

We illustrate the concept of complementary relatedness density in GVCs by presenting a particular example of the Italian region of Friuli-Venezia Giulia. The logistics industry is crucial in the region since Trieste has the biggest port of Italy in terms of annual cargo tonnage. However, the region is primarily specialised in low complex functions in the logistics industry, such as customer services clerks, sales and services elementary occupations, and drivers and mobile-plant operators. In this vein, a more preferable functional specialisation in the logistics industry could be physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals, which is the most complex function inside the logistics industry.

By moving from more manufacturing-alike functions towards more science-related functions, the region could leverage on their own local capabilities but also on complementary capabilities in partner regions in GVCs. In the map on the left hand-side of [Figure 1](#), the bilateral complementarity relatedness density (BCRD) is shown, meaning the potential complementary relatedness density that could be offered by all EU regions. It represents the functions that are related to physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals in logistics in which Friuli-Venezia Giulia is not specialised but in which EU regions are specialised to a greater or lesser extent. The higher its value, the higher the level of complementary capabilities in EU regions that are missing in Friuli-Venezia Giulia. BCRDs are generally low for Italian regions. The highest complementarities can be found in regions such as Antwerp, Jutland, Slovenia, Helsinki and the Baltic countries which are also important regions in maritime logistics.

While these regions are in the position to potentially offer the highest complementary capabilities, the extent to which Friuli-Venezia Giulia could benefit from them depends on the strength of GVC linkages. As it happens in trade, national borders and geographical proximity matter: Friuli-Venezia Giulia tends to trade more inside Italy and with its neighbouring regions. This is depicted in the map on the right-hand side of [Figure 1](#), which shows the complementary relatedness densities once weighted by the share of value added imported from each region (inside the summation in equation 5). It can be observed that, compared to the left map, other Italian and Austrian regions are playing a more prominent role in providing complementary capabilities, once considering the existing real GVC linkages. While some Irish, Danish and Spanish regions remain important, others like Antwerp, Latvia, and Lithuania fade, due to their low value added trade with Friuli-Venezia Giulia.

This framework for mapping complementary capabilities through the concept of complementary relatedness density can be developed for every region and every function

Figure 1. BCRD (left) and the real contribution to the complementary relatedness density (right) for physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals in logistics for Friuli-venezia Giulia in the period 2008–2010.

in GVCs. This framework can help policy-makers to prioritise partnerships with other EU regions offering complementary capabilities across value chains. This complementary relatedness density measure can provide an illustration of what potential EU partner regions can leverage complementary capabilities to foster functional upgrading in regions and to avoid functional downgrading in global value chains.

3.5. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 displays the main descriptive statistics of the variables. The number of observations for upgrading, diversification, downgrading, and exit, is overall lower than for the rest of variables, since if a region is already (–un)specialised in a function, it cannot become (–un) specialised again in the subsequent period. Table 1 provides individual descriptive statistics including the observations used in the regression analyses. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that upgrading and downgrading consists of a subset of diversification and exit, respectively. Therefore, the number of observations is notably lower in the case of upgrading and downgrading than for diversification and exit, respectively.⁴

⁴Since each dependent variable (upgrading, diversification, downgrading, and exit) has different number of observations, individual descriptive statistics are provided in Table 1. The overall descriptive statistics are provided in Appendix B. Appendix C provides the correlation matrix. Notice that since upgrading/diversification and downgrading/exit are mutually exclusive, it is not possible to show the correlation between them.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics by the individual samples used in the regressions.

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
A) Upgrading					
Upgrading	13,742	0.141	0.348	0	1
Local rel. dens.	13,742	0.396	0.074	0	0.662
Compl. rel. dens.	13,742	0.142	0.033	0.055	0.315
GDP pc	13,742	22,503.567	8,443.523	8,040.041	68,114.922
GVC part.	13,742	0.642	0.102	0.341	0.838
Pop. dens.	13,742	223.188	550.984	3.3	6,744.633
Patents	13,742	528.331	1,024.702	0	9,324.06
FSI	13,742	0.141	0.348	0	1
FCI_s	13,742	2.021	1.47	-1.18	5.313
B) Diversification					
Diversification	24,552	0.148	0.355	0	1
Local rel. dens.	24,552	0.395	0.078	0	0.686
Compl. rel. dens.	24,552	0.141	0.032	0.054	0.315
GDP pc	24,552	23,855.949	8,832.974	8,040.041	68,114.922
GVC part.	24,552	0.645	0.09	0.341	0.838
Pop. dens.	24,552	286.955	687.678	3.3	6,744.633
Patents	24,552	825.956	1,415.696	0	9,324.06
FSI	24,552	0.148	0.355	0	1
FCI_s	24,552	0.395	2.294	-3.8	5.313
C) Downgrading					
Downgrading	8,041	0.228	0.42	0	1
Local rel. dens.	8,041	0.442	0.069	0.008	0.673
Compl. rel. dens.	8,041	0.137	0.029	0.056	0.311
GDP pc	8,041	23,904.848	8,836.509	8,040.041	68,114.922
GVC part.	8,041	0.643	0.089	0.341	0.838
Pop. dens.	8,041	313.16	733.603	3.3	6,744.633
Patents	8,041	792.894	1,347.726	0	9,324.06
FSI	8,041	0.772	0.42	0	1
FCI_s	8,041	1.687	1.548	-1.18	5.313
D) Exit					
Exit	16,566	0.215	0.411	0	1
Local rel. dens.	16,566	0.446	0.072	0.006	0.682
Compl. rel. dens.	16,566	0.135	0.029	0.051	0.311
GDP pc	16,566	23,870.257	8,796.925	8,040.041	68,114.922
GVC part.	16,566	0.644	0.089	0.341	0.838
Pop. dens.	16,566	301.041	703.776	3.3	6,744.633
Patents	16,566	774.072	1,328.623	0	9,324.06
FSI	16,566	0.785	0.411	0	1
FCI_s	16,566	-0.02	2.171	-3.8	5.313

All four dependent variables (upgrading, diversification, downgrading, and exit) are dummies variables, taking values 0 and 1. The variable local relatedness density captures the existence of local related capabilities. Particularly, it shows the percentage of related functions in which the region is already specialised. The variable complementary relatedness density captures the intensity of complementary capabilities that regions are exposed to across GVCs. Finally, while *FSI* accounts for the specialisation of regions in functions, 1 being specialised and 0 otherwise, FCI_s displays the complexity of the functions in which regions upgrade, diversify, downgrade, and exit, respectively. Note that in the summary statistics, the number of observations are different across the four models we are estimating. This is because if a region is already specialised (un-specialised) in a certain function, the next period it cannot become again specialised (un-specialised).

4. Empirical framework

We use fixed effect linear probability models (LPMs) because all the dependent variables are dummy variables.⁵ These models have the following general specification:

$$Y_{rst} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Local Rel Den}_{rs,t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Compl Rel Den}_{rs,t-1} + \gamma X_{r,t-1} + \varphi_r + \mu_s + \theta_t + \varepsilon_{rst} \quad (15)$$

As stated before, four dependent variables (Y_{rst}) are used: functional upgrading, diversification, downgrading, and exit. The two main variables of interest are the local relatedness density (LRD) and the complementary relatedness density (CRD) for each region (r) and each function (s) in the previous time period ($t-1$). While the LRD captures the existence of local related capabilities, the CRD captures complementary non-local capabilities through global value chains. The models also add an interaction term between the two variables to test whether both local relatedness density and the complementary relatedness density have a positive (negative) effect on the likelihood of functional upgrading (downgrading) in GVCs.

The models also include a vector of control variables at the regional level ($X_{r,t-1}$), and region, function and time fixed effects ($\varphi_r, \mu_s, \theta_t$). The control variables include: (1) GDP per capita, as a proxy for the level of regional development; (2) population density, measured as population by square kilometer, as a proxy for agglomeration externalities; (3) number of patent applications, as a proxy for regional stocks of technological knowledge; and (4) GVC participation, as a proxy for the ability of regions to participate in GVCs. These control variables are all in logarithm to control for excess kurtosis. To account for the presence of heteroskedasticity, standard errors are clustered at the regional level in all regressions. All independent variables are lagged by one period and mean centred. The time periods (t) refer to four time windows, namely 2000–2001, 2002–2004, 2005–2007, 2008–2010. $\varepsilon_{r,s,t}$ stands for the regression residual.

5. Results

Table 2 shows the results for the role of complementary interregional value chain linkages in the functional diversification and upgrading of EU regions in GVCs. Complementary relatedness density (CRD) is positively and significantly associated with higher chances of experiencing both functional diversification (models 1–3) and upgrading (models 4–6) in value chains. Particularly, the coefficients from the full models (2 and 5) suggest that one standard deviation increase in the CRD leads to a 6.5 and 5 percentage points increase in the likelihood of functional diversification and upgrading, respectively.⁶ This leads to validate hypotheses 1a and 1b. The effects are large

⁵Traditionally, the literature on entry/exit models preferred linear probability models over logit and probit specifications. This is due to a potential bias or inconsistency when estimating these models with a large number of dummy variables and different fixed effects (Greene 2012). In any case, similar results were obtained using logit and probits models, as shown in Appendices IV and V, respectively. Furthermore, results hold after controlling for human capital, proxied by the percentage of population with tertiary education, and for regional industrial structures, proxied by the share of gross value added generated by the manufacturing sector, as shown in Appendix F Data for both control variables was retrieved from Eurostat. Appendix G provides regressions using different thresholds around the FSI: diversification and upgrading from $FSI_{r,s,t-1} < 0.9$ to $FSI_{r,s,t} \geq 1$ and, exit and downgrading from $FSI_{r,s,t-1} \geq 1.1$ to $FSI_{r,s,t} < 1$

⁶These results are obtained by multiplying the coefficients from models 2 and 5 in Table 2 with the standard deviation (SD) of the complementary relatedness density in the respective subsamples of diversification and upgrading (see Table 1). Namely, 2.028×0.032 and 1.470×0.033 . The same is then repeated for exit and downgrading using the coefficients from models 2 and 5 in Table 3.

Table 2. Complementary interregional value chain linkages and functional diversification and upgrading.

	LPMs					
	Diversification			Upgrading		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Baseline	Full Model	Interaction	Baseline	Full Model	Interaction
Local rel. dens.	0.899*** (0.0683)	1.609*** (0.0956)	1.635*** (0.0934)	0.953*** (0.0863)	1.310*** (0.125)	1.340*** (0.125)
Compl. rel. dens.	0.919*** (0.167)	2.028*** (0.306)	1.651*** (0.269)	0.920*** (0.207)	1.470*** (0.347)	1.093*** (0.335)
Interaction			-4.947*** (0.903)			-5.098*** (1.138)
GDP pc (log)		0.0528 (0.107)	0.0566 (0.109)		0.0526 (0.101)	0.0536 (0.101)
Pop. dens. (log)		-0.474** (0.195)	-0.463** (0.203)		-0.244 (0.203)	-0.240 (0.211)
GVC part. (log)		0.417*** (0.153)	0.448*** (0.159)		0.219* (0.123)	0.233* (0.126)
Patents (log)		-0.00901 (0.0165)	-0.00634 (0.0167)		-0.00692 (0.0149)	-0.00454 (0.0151)
Constant	0.164*** (0.00411)	0.172*** (0.00514)	0.168*** (0.00497)	0.158*** (0.00533)	0.118*** (0.0418)	0.117*** (0.0435)
Observations	24,552	24,552	24,552	13,743	13,742	13,742
R ²	0.026	0.070	0.071	0.027	0.090	0.092
Region FEs	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES
Function FEs	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES
Period FEs	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$ level.

in magnitude, in view that the unconditional probability of diversification is only around 15%, and 14% for upgrading, as shown in Table 1. Thus, regions can leverage on complementary capabilities from value chain partners to diversify and upgrade in more complex functions in value chains.

Consistent with previous research, the local relatedness density (LRD) is also positively and significantly associated with the likelihood of functional diversification and upgrading. One standard deviation increase in the LRD leads to a 12.6 and 9.7 percentage points increase in the likelihood of functional diversification and upgrading, respectively. These effects are about the double in magnitude compared to those of the CRD a region obtains from its trade partners. While complementary non-local capabilities can help regions to diversify and upgrade in functions across GVCs, local capabilities remain crucial and have a more sizeable effect on functional diversification and upgrading in value chains in EU regions.

The interaction between local and complementary relatedness densities turns out to be negative and significant for both diversification and upgrading. This points towards a substitution effect. On the one hand, regions with stronger local capabilities depend less on non-local sources of knowledge for diversifying and upgrading into more complex functions in GVCs. On the other hand, regions with more connections with other regions offering complementary capabilities need to rely less on their own existing capabilities. Then, the complementary relatedness density obtained from trade partners plays a more important role for functional upgrading

Table 3. Complementary interregional value chain linkages and functional exit and downgrading.

	LPMs					
	Exit			Downgrading		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Baseline	Full Model	Interaction	Baseline	Full Model	Interaction
Local rel. dens.	-0.948*** (0.101)	-1.743*** (0.149)	-1.730*** (0.150)	-0.944*** (0.129)	-1.811*** (0.200)	-1.805*** (0.200)
Compl. rel. dens.	-0.271 (0.297)	-2.306*** (0.439)	-2.361*** (0.442)	-0.325 (0.386)	-3.217*** (0.587)	-3.223*** (0.589)
Interaction			4.398* (2.507)			3.221 (3.371)
GDP pc (log)		-0.0627 (0.117)	-0.0510 (0.118)		-0.0857 (0.154)	-0.0764 (0.154)
Pop. dens. (log)		-0.0130 (0.346)	-0.0359 (0.346)		-0.321 (0.424)	-0.337 (0.424)
GVC part. (log)		-0.0210 (0.215)	-0.0392 (0.216)		-0.0453 (0.298)	-0.0568 (0.297)
Patents (log)		-0.0241 (0.0152)	-0.0281* (0.0156)		-0.0529*** (0.0193)	-0.0559*** (0.0193)
Constant	0.245*** (0.00682)	0.264*** (0.00638)	0.268*** (0.00691)	0.254*** (0.00877)	0.285*** (0.0143)	0.289*** (0.0150)
Observations	16,566	16,566	16,566	8,042	8,041	8,041
R ²	0.022	0.097	0.097	0.019	0.124	0.124
Region FEs	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES
Function FEs	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES
Period FEs	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$ level.

and diversification in regions lacking local capabilities. This is shown in [Figure 2](#), where the marginal effects of the CRD on the entry (left) and upgrading (right) are plotted at different levels of LRD. In addition, it is interesting to highlight that while previous research found a positive and significant correlation between GVC participation and upgrading in value chains (Hernández-Rodríguez et al. 2025), when introducing the CRD, this effect considerably decreases. This is consistent with literature: interregional linkages are not *per se* sufficient, but what really matters are complementary interregional linkages (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma and Iammarino 2009).

Figure 2. Marginal effects of complementary relatedness density on entry (left) and upgrading (right) at different levels of local relatedness density.

Figure 3. Marginal effects of complementary relatedness density on exit (left) and downgrading (right) at different levels of local relatedness density.

Table 3 presents the results for the role of interregional value chain linkages in functional exit and downgrading for EU regions. As expected, complementary interregional linkages reduce the chances of regions to exit (models 1–3) and downgrade (models 4–6) in functions along value chains. In the full models, a one standard deviation increase in CRD leads to a 6.7 and 9.3 percentage points lower likelihood of exiting and downgrading functions in GVCs, respectively, compared to their unconditional probabilities of 21.5% and 22.8%. This leads to validate hypotheses 2a and 2b. These results highlight that being engaged in value chains in which partner regions offer complementary capabilities reduces the chances of exiting and downgrading functions in value chains.

Again, as expected, the local relatedness density is found to be negatively and significantly associated with both functional exit and downgrading. A one standard deviation increase in LRD leads to about 12.5 percentage points decrease in the chances of both functional exit and downgrading. In line with the results for functional diversification and upgrading, local capabilities are found to be more relevant to prevent functional exit and downgrading than complementary capabilities. While both local and complementary capabilities matter when it comes to preserve the specialisation in complex functions in value chains, this effect is larger for local capabilities.

The interaction term between local and complementary relatedness density is not found to be significant for exit and downgrading. Although the sign of the coefficient points towards a substitution effect, the lack of statistical significance suggests that for retaining specialisations in complex functions in GVCs, local and complementary capabilities act through different channels. This substitution effect can be observed in Figure 3, where the marginal effects of CRD on exit (left) and downgrading (right) at different levels of LRD are displayed. The negative effect of CRD on both functional exit and downgrading decreases when regions have stronger local capabilities, although the difference is insignificant when comparing regions with different LRD.

6. Conclusions

The increasing relevance of global value chains and, particularly, the uneven spatial distribution of production functions impose several challenges to regions (Antràs 2020; Gereffi 1999; Los, Timmer, and De Vries 2015; Timmer et al. 2015, 2019). Since different

production functions generate different levels of value added, regions seek to move up and climb the ladder of functions in GVCs (Capello and Dellisanti 2024; Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon 2005; Giuliani, Pietrobelli, and Rabellotti 2005; Humphrey and Schmitz 2002; Ponte and Ewert 2009). Thus, it has become crucial for regions to upgrade into more complex functions in GVCs and to retain such functions over time, avoiding functional downgrading (Blažek 2016; Buciuni, Canello, and Gereffi 2022; Gereffi 2019).⁷

This paper aimed to tackle the question on how interregional value chain linkages across 199 EU regions can act as a source of non-local capabilities to foster functional upgrading and to avoid functional downgrading. The empirical analysis used relatedness and economic complexity metrics by combining three sources of data: interregional input-output tables, regional labour structures, and regional income shares. Results show that regions exposed to complementary capabilities through GVCs are associated with a higher likelihood of functional upgrading. That is, they are more likely to upgrade into more complex functions in GVCs. Moreover, regions exposed to complementary capabilities through GVCs are associated with a lower likelihood of functional downgrading. In other words, they are less likely to downgrade and lose complex functions in GVCs.

Overall, these findings contribute to the further integration between EEG and GVC literatures (Boschma 2022, 2024; H. W. C. Yeung 2021, 2024). First, this paper points out how EEG concepts such as complementary capabilities, using relatedness and economic complexity metrics, are useful for studying upgrading and downgrading of GVCs (De Propris 2024; Poon 2024). Such metrics could also be used for other issues beyond upgrading and downgrading, such as strategic coupling (Coe and Yeung 2015; Horner 2014; MacKinnon 2012; H. W. Yeung 2015). Second, this paper introduces the role of interregional value chains linkages in evolutionary models of regional diversification, complementing the role of local capabilities (Boschma 2017; Tripl, Grillitsch, and Isaksen 2018). It underlines the importance of complementary linkages over linkages in general, meaning that linkages *per se* are necessary but not sufficient (Balland and Boschma 2021; Boschma and Iammarino 2009). Third, this paper studies these issues at the subnational level, uncovering regional differences across the EU in functions in GVCs (Crescenzi and Iammarino 2017; Iammarino 2018; Los, Timmer, and De Vries 2015).

However, there are also limitations that need to be acknowledged. First, while this paper relies on the best possible sources of data available, it suffers from certain issues. For example, the time frame remains relatively short to capture large structural transformations such as functional upgrading and downgrading in GVCs. Also, the industrial classifications of sectors provided in EUREGIO and EULFS/EUSES are quite aggregated, limiting the level of granularity for the empirical analysis. Second, this paper focuses on economic upgrading and downgrading. There are also other dimensions that could be explored when looking at regional participation in GVCs, such as environmental and social downgrading

⁷However, it is also important to point out that downgrading can be sometimes beneficial. As shown in Amighini and Rabellotti (2006), local leading firms in the Riviera del Brenta successfully generated linkages in related GVC functions and repositioned themselves in the global economy by downgrading their existing functions. Also, Gibbon and Ponte (2005) underlined how product downgrading can be the most profitable strategy for some firms in the short run due to economies of scale.

(Barrientos, Gereffi, and Pickles 2016; Bolwig et al. 2010; Breau and Rigby 2010; Krishnan, De Marchi, and Ponte 2023; Lund-Thomsen and Nadvi 2010; Ponte and Gibbon 2005). Third, the role of institutions in GVCs has been left unexplored in this paper. The literature has, however, underlined how regional institutions are crucial to help regions to benefit from GVCs, but also to avoid unintended negative consequences of GVCs (Pardy 2024; Rodríguez-Pose 2021).

Furthermore, this paper opens new windows for future research. First, while this paper focuses on complementary capabilities, it does not dig into other proximity dimensions such as cognitive, geographical, or social proximities (Boschma 2005). EU regions may find it easier to connect in GVCs with neighbour regions, and particularly with regions within the same country (Bachtrögler-Unger et al. 2023; Bolea et al. 2022). Second, the EU is strongly calling for ensuring the resilience of the EU value chains and its strategic autonomy. The framework presented in this paper provides instruments to develop further analysis looking at the roles of EU regions in GVCs and their implications for resilience (Balland, Rigby, and Boschma 2015; Boschma 2015; Steijn et al. 2023; Xiao, Boschma, and Andersson 2018). Third, although this paper looked at the negative side of GVCs in terms of functional downgrading, nothing has been said regarding other dimensions such as social rights, working conditions and the threat of rising intra- and interregional inequality. On this particular matter, more insights to understand how regional institutions shape these issues remain crucial (Barbero et al. 2021; Morgan 2007; Pardy 2024; Rodríguez-Pose 2013, 2021). Also, the role of institutions is key to better understand how power is shared among actors and how this shapes the governance of GVCs (Capello, Dellisanti, and Perucca 2023; Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon 2005; Gibbon and Ponte 2008; Nadvi 2008; Humphrey and Schmitz 2000). The role of MNEs, the presence of strong regional institutions, and power relationships in the governance of GVCs are fundamental to understand how the benefits from GVCs are distributed. In this particular vein, more research is needed to explore underlying heterogeneities across EU regions in terms of geographical distribution, levels of economic development, and institutional quality.

Finally, it is possible to draw some policy implications from the findings of this paper. While related regional capabilities are found to remain fundamental for triggering functional upgrading and diversification in GVCs, regions can also leverage on complementary non-local capabilities to do so. In this sense, regional policies such as Smart Specialisation should promote collaboration and trade partnership with other EU regions specialised in different but complementary stages of the value chains. Current Smart Specialisation Strategies focus little attention on interregional linkages, particularly to GVCs dynamics (Barzotto et al. 2019; Giustolisi, Benner, and Trippel 2023; Iacobucci and Guzzini 2016; Radosevic and Stancova 2015; Santoalha 2019; Thissen et al. 2013; Uyarra, Marzocchi, and Sorvik 2018; Varga et al. 2020). The framework proposed here can be instrumental for finding strategic partner regions offering complementary capabilities to promote upgrading and to prevent downgrading in GVCs.

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Appendices

Appendix A.- Lists of the 199 EU regions and 77 functions included in the analysis

A) List of the 199 EU regions (NUTS-2) included in the analysis

AT11	CZ07	DEA1	ES23	FR30	GR42	ITF3	PT15
AT12	CZ08	DEA2	ES24	FR41	GR43	ITF4	PT16
AT13	DE11	DEA3	ES30	FR42	HU10	ITF5	PT17
AT21	DE12	DEA4	ES41	FR43	HU21	ITF6	PT18
AT22	DE13	DEA5	ES42	FR51	HU22	ITG1	SE11
AT31	DE14	DEB1	ES43	FR52	HU23	ITG2	SE12
AT32	DE21	DEB2	ES51	FR53	HU31	LT00	SE21
AT33	DE22	DEB3	ES52	FR61	HU32	LU00	SE22
AT34	DE23	DEC0	ES53	FR62	HU33	LV00	SE23
BE10	DE24	DED1	ES61	FR63	IE01	PL11	SE31
BE21	DE25	DED2	ES62	FR71	IE02	PL12	SE32
BE22	DE26	DED3	ES63	FR72	ITC1	PL21	SE33
BE23	DE27	DEE1	ES64	FR81	ITC2	PL22	SI00
BE24	DE30	DEE2	ES70	FR82	ITC3	PL31	SK01
BE25	DE41	DEE3	FI13	FR83	ITC4	PL32	SK02
BE31	DE42	DEF0	FI18	GR11	ITD1	PL33	SK03
BE32	DE50	DEG0	FI19	GR12	ITD2	PL34	SK04
BE33	DE60	DK01	FI1A	GR13	ITD3	PL41	
BE34	DE71	DK02	FI20	GR14	ITD4	PL42	
BE35	DE72	DK03	FR10	GR21	ITD5	PL43	
CZ01	DE73	EE00	FR21	GR22	ITE1	PL51	
CZ02	DE80	ES11	FR22	GR23	ITE2	PL52	
CZ03	DE91	ES12	FR23	GR24	ITE3	PL61	
CZ04	DE92	ES13	FR24	GR25	ITE4	PL62	
CZ05	DE93	ES21	FR25	GR30	ITF1	PL63	
CZ06	DE94	ES22	FR26	GR41	ITF2	PT11	

B) List of the 77 functions included in the analysis

Occupation	Industry	Occupation	Industry
Customer services clerks	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Other associate professionals	Professional services and real estate development
Customer services clerks	Professional services and real estate development	Other associate professionals	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Customer services clerks	Financial intermediation	Other associate professionals	Manufacturing and mining
Customer services clerks	Logistics	Other associate professionals	Logistics
Customer services clerks	Manufacturing and mining	Other associate professionals	Financial intermediation
Drivers and mobile-plant operators	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Other craft and related trades workers	Professional services and real estate development
Drivers and mobile-plant operators	Manufacturing and mining	Other craft and related trades workers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Drivers and mobile-plant operators	Professional services and real estate development	Other craft and related trades workers	Manufacturing and mining
Drivers and mobile-plant operators	Logistics	Other professionals	Manufacturing and mining
Extraction and building trades workers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Other professionals	Professional services and real estate development
Extraction and building trades workers	Manufacturing and mining	Other professionals	Logistics
Extraction and building trades workers	Professional services and real estate development	Other professionals	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
General managers	Professional services and real estate development	Other professionals	Financial intermediation

(Continued)

(Continued).

Occupation	Industry	Occupation	Industry
General managers	Financial intermediation	Personal and protective services workers	Manufacturing and mining
General managers	Logistics	Personal and protective services workers	Logistics
General managers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Personal and protective services workers	Professional services and real estate development
General managers	Manufacturing and mining	Personal and protective services workers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Labourers in mining, construction, manufacturing and transport	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Physical and engineering science associate professionals	Manufacturing and mining
Labourers in mining, construction, manufacturing and transport	Manufacturing and mining	Physical and engineering science associate professionals	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Labourers in mining, construction, manufacturing and transport	Logistics	Physical and engineering science associate professionals	Financial intermediation
Labourers in mining, construction, manufacturing and transport	Professional services and real estate development	Physical and engineering science associate professionals	Professional services and real estate development
Life science employees	Professional services and real estate development	Physical and engineering science associate professionals	Logistics
Life science employees	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals	Manufacturing and mining
Life science employees	Manufacturing and mining	Physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Machine operators and assemblers	Professional services and real estate development	Physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals	Professional services and real estate development
Machine operators and assemblers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals	Financial intermediation
Machine operators and assemblers	Manufacturing and mining	Physical, mathematical and engineering science professionals	Logistics
Metal, machinery and related trades workers	Manufacturing and mining	Precision, handicraft, printing and related trades workers	Manufacturing and mining
Metal, machinery and related trades workers	Professional services and real estate development	Sales and services elementary occupations	Professional services and real estate development
Metal, machinery and related trades workers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Sales and services elementary occupations	Manufacturing and mining
Metal, machinery and related trades workers	Logistics	Sales and services elementary occupations	Logistics
Models, salespersons and demonstrators	Manufacturing and mining	Sales and services elementary occupations	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Models, salespersons and demonstrators	Professional services and real estate development	Stationary-plant and related operators	Manufacturing and mining
Models, salespersons and demonstrators	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Corporate managers	Professional services and real estate development
Office clerks	Professional services and real estate development	Corporate managers	Manufacturing and mining
Office clerks	Manufacturing and mining	Corporate managers	Financial intermediation
Office clerks	Wholesale, retail, and tourism	Corporate managers	Logistics
Office clerks	Financial intermediation	Corporate managers	Wholesale, retail, and tourism
Office clerks	Logistics		

Appendix B. Overall descriptive statistics

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
FSI	60,368	0.404	0.491	0	1
FCI _s	60,368	0.228	2.255	-3.8	5.313
Local rel. dens.	60,368	0.416	0.078	0	0.686
Compl. rel. dens.	60,368	0.14	0.032	0.031	0.315
Upgrading	15,238	0.141	0.348	0	1
Diversification	26,960	0.148	0.355	0	1
Downgrading	8,833	0.229	0.421	0	1
Exit	18,239	0.216	0.411	0	1
GDP per capita	60,368	22,322.961	8,896.779	6,533.932	68,114.922
Population dens.	56,133	286.387	679.43	3.3	6,744.633
GVC participation	60,368	0.636	0.088	0.341	0.838
Patents	60,368	684.168	1,242.329	0	9,324.06

Appendix C. Correlation matrix

Notice that upgrading/diversification and downgrading/exit are mutually exclusive, meaning that they cannot be observed at the same time. Therefore, the correlation between such variables cannot be computed. Furthermore, upgrading and downgrading are subsets of diversification and exit, respectively. Thus, they are perfectly correlated. However, they are used in different equations as dependent variables, which should not imply any empirical issue.

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) Diversification	1.000									
(2) Upgrading	1.000	1.000								
(3) Exit	.	.	1.000							
(4) Downgrading	.	.	1.000	1.000						
(5) Local rel. dens.	0.208	0.207	-0.228	-0.215	1.000					
(6) Comp. rel. dens.	-0.027	-0.026	0.084	0.070	-0.486	1.000				
(7) GDP pc	-0.013	0.020	-0.021	-0.076	-0.125	-0.027	1.000			
(8) Pop. dens.	-0.019	0.014	-0.028	-0.059	-0.008	-0.027	0.435	1.000		
(9) GVC part.	0.017	0.018	0.047	0.046	-0.051	0.169	0.067	-0.040	1.000	
(10) Patents	-0.033	0.016	-0.008	-0.065	-0.202	0.004	0.447	0.109	-0.013	1.000

Appendix D. Logit models

	Logit: Average marginal effects			
	(1) Diversification	(2) Upgrading	(3) Exit	(4) Downgrading
Local rel. dens.	1.610*** (0.0861)	1.350*** (0.116)	-1.682*** (0.136)	-1.686*** (0.188)
Compl. rel. dens.	1.837*** (0.255)	1.532*** (0.327)	-2.289*** (0.417)	-3.023*** (0.561)
GDP pc (log)	0.0353 (0.112)	0.0610 (0.118)	-0.0995 (0.134)	-0.127 (0.183)
Pop. Den. (log)	-0.508** (0.203)	-0.239 (0.227)	-0.0685 (0.388)	-0.424 (0.467)
GVC part. (log)	0.467*** (0.168)	0.289 (0.176)	-0.00300 (0.228)	-0.0365 (0.295)
Patents (log)	-0.00859 (0.0171)	-0.00612 (0.0165)	-0.0258* (0.0151)	-0.0493*** (0.0174)
Observations	24,552	13,742	16,566	8,041
Period FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Region FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Function FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$ level.

Appendix E. Probit models

	Probit: Average marginal effects			
	(1) Diversification	(2) Upgrading	(3) Exit	(4) Downgrading
Local rel. dens.	1.599*** (0.0849)	1.336*** (0.114)	-1.660*** (0.136)	-1.694*** (0.185)
Compl. rel. dens.	1.817*** (0.253)	1.477*** (0.326)	-2.190*** (0.418)	-3.013*** (0.557)
GDP pc (log)	0.0566 (0.111)	0.0661 (0.115)	-0.0816 (0.127)	-0.128 (0.178)
Pop. Den. (log)	-0.468** (0.199)	-0.201 (0.228)	-0.0468 (0.369)	-0.411 (0.453)
GVC part. (log)	0.443*** (0.157)	0.249 (0.160)	0.00211 (0.227)	-0.0573 (0.296)
Patents (log)	-0.00919 (0.0168)	-0.00559 (0.0158)	-0.0246 (0.0153)	-0.0502*** (0.0178)
Observations	24,552	13,742	16,566	8,041
Period FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Region FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES
Function FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$ level.

Appendix F. LPMs with additional control variables: human capital and industrial structures

	LPMs with additional controls							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	Diversification	Diversification	Upgrading	Upgrading	Exit	Exit	Downgrading	Downgrading
Local rel. dens.	1.616*** (0.0970)	1.642*** (0.0952)	1.310*** (0.126)	1.341*** (0.127)	-1.844*** (0.153)	-1.828*** (0.154)	-1.936*** (0.206)	-1.930*** (0.207)
Compl. rel. dens.	2.045*** (0.301)	1.681*** (0.275)	1.457*** (0.344)	1.096*** (0.336)	-2.573*** (0.455)	-2.640*** (0.459)	-3.520*** (0.609)	-3.534*** (0.612)
Interaction		-4.849*** (0.894)		-4.990*** (1.186)		5.078** (2.348)		3.931 (3.289)
GDP pc (log)	0.0397 (0.126)	0.0458 (0.129)	0.0839 (0.121)	0.0903 (0.123)	-0.128 (0.139)	-0.113 (0.141)	-0.139 (0.197)	-0.126 (0.196)
Pop. dens. (log)	-0.439** (0.194)	-0.443** (0.205)	-0.307 (0.194)	-0.314 (0.203)	0.118 (0.308)	0.0927 (0.310)	-0.187 (0.406)	-0.205 (0.409)
GVC part. (log)	0.419*** (0.156)	0.453*** (0.163)	0.274** (0.134)	0.286** (0.138)	-0.135 (0.218)	-0.157 (0.219)	-0.214 (0.307)	-0.228 (0.306)
Patents (log)	-0.00159 (0.0168)	0.000579 (0.0171)	-0.00208 (0.0149)	-0.000180 (0.0151)	-0.0177 (0.0162)	-0.0223 (0.0166)	-0.0476** (0.0208)	-0.0511** (0.0210)
Education (log)	-0.0647 (0.0452)	-0.0522 (0.0436)	-0.0815 (0.0525)	-0.0670 (0.0515)	-0.159** (0.0687)	-0.165** (0.0684)	-0.131* (0.0753)	-0.136* (0.0755)
Industrial share (log)	0.0255 (0.0856)	0.0160 (0.0871)	-0.105 (0.0920)	-0.117 (0.0938)	0.0229 (0.131)	0.0206 (0.131)	0.0698 (0.174)	0.0664 (0.175)
Constant	0.172*** (0.00679)	0.169*** (0.00645)	0.103** (0.0418)	0.102** (0.0432)	0.255*** (0.00857)	0.260*** (0.00894)	0.276*** (0.0162)	0.280*** (0.0169)
Observations	23,859	23,859	13,345	13,345	16,027	16,027	7,781	7,781
R ²	0.071	0.072	0.091	0.092	0.101	0.102	0.126	0.126
Region FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Function FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Period FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$ level.

Appendix G. LPMs using different thresholds around the FSIs

	LPMs							
	Diversification		Upgrading		Exit		Downgrading	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	Full Model	Interaction	Full Model	Interaction	Full Model	Interaction	Full Model	Interaction
Local rel. dens.	1.319*** (0.0892)	1.339*** (0.0878)	1.064*** (0.119)	1.085*** (0.119)	-1.417*** (0.144)	-1.403*** (0.144)	-1.438*** (0.197)	-1.435*** (0.197)
Compl. rel. dens.	1.923*** (0.275)	1.664*** (0.265)	1.471*** (0.323)	1.223*** (0.331)	-1.879*** (0.410)	-1.946*** (0.414)	-2.526*** (0.535)	-2.530*** (0.536)
Interaction		-3.207*** (0.970)		-3.192*** (1.194)		4.641** (2.260)		1.678 (3.406)
GDP pc (log)	0.0109 (0.0973)	0.0148 (0.0991)	-0.0494 (0.0918)	-0.0471 (0.0928)	-0.121 (0.101)	-0.110 (0.101)	-0.182 (0.143)	-0.177 (0.143)
Pop. dens. (log)	-0.392** (0.168)	-0.386** (0.172)	-0.214 (0.172)	-0.213 (0.175)	-0.274 (0.315)	-0.297 (0.316)	-0.651 (0.411)	-0.659 (0.413)
GVC part. (log)	0.328** (0.136)	0.352** (0.139)	0.134 (0.110)	0.146 (0.112)	-0.0284 (0.220)	-0.0465 (0.221)	-0.0486 (0.314)	-0.0547 (0.314)
Patents (log)	-0.00571 (0.0162)	-0.00404 (0.0163)	-0.00354 (0.0161)	-0.00211 (0.0163)	-0.0100 (0.0131)	-0.0142 (0.0134)	-0.0238 (0.0173)	-0.0253 (0.0174)
Constant	0.136*** (0.00515)	0.134*** (0.00506)	0.0798** (0.0371)	0.0793** (0.0377)	0.211*** (0.00847)	0.215*** (0.00871)	0.243*** (0.0134)	0.245*** (0.0143)
Observations	22,176	22,176	12,506	12,506	14,287	14,287	6,830	6,830
R ²	0.070	0.071	0.087	0.088	0.111	0.112	0.145	0.145
Region FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Function FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Period FEs	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

All independent variables are mean centred and lagged by one period. Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors (clustered at the regional level) are shown in parentheses. Sample in columns 1, 2, 3, and 4 only includes those with $FSI_{r,s,t-1} < 0.9$, and in columns 5, 6, 7, and 8 only those with $FSI_{r,s,t-1} > 1.1$. Coefficients are statistically significant at the * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$ level.